

Feasibility of using printed polymer transducers for mid-air haptic feedback

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Abstract— Recently, there has been considerable interest in the development of ultrasound based mid-air haptic feedback devices. These devices allow for tactile sensations to be induced at any position and time without constraints to human motion, which is useful for virtual user interfaces, augmented/virtual reality and feedback buttons. The haptic feedback mechanism is a combination of acoustic streaming and radiation force. Most work reported in literature induce said effects using matrices of ‘standard’ single element transducers, which are rigid, bulky and heavy. Our research focuses on the development of printed polymer transducers (PPTs): piezomembranes deposited using a printing process. As PPTs are fully flexible, < 0.25 mm thick and light, they can be easily integrated onto curved surfaces. However, the piezoelectric charge coefficients of P(VDF-TrFE) are low compared to regular PZT5A/H, making it challenging to achieve the required sound pressure. This work investigates the feasibility of using PPTs for haptic feedback using simulations and laser vibrometer- and acoustic measurements. The peak pressure produced by our chosen array design was calculated to amount to radiation forces approximately 10x larger than the tactile radiation force threshold reported in literature. Thus using PPTs for haptic feedback appears feasible.

Keywords—mid-air haptic feedback; radiation force; acoustic streaming; flexible ultrasound sources; PVDF

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been considerable interest in the development of ultrasound based mid-air haptic feedback devices. These devices allow for tactile sensations to be induced at any position and time without constraints to human motion, which is useful for virtual user interfaces, augmented and virtual reality, feedback buttons and touch-free interaction with television screens. The haptic feedback mechanism is a combination of acoustic streaming and radiation force. Most work reported in literature induce the aforementioned effects using matrices of ‘standard’ single element transducers, which are rigid, bulky and heavy [1,2]. Our research focuses on the development of printed polymer transducers (PPTs): piezomembranes deposited using a printing process. The membrane is a sandwich of polyimide and P(VDF-TrFE). As PPTs are fully flexible, < 0.25 mm thick and light, they can be easily integrated onto curved surfaces. However, the piezoelectric charge coefficients of P(VDF-TrFE) are low compared to regular PZT5A/H, making it challenging to achieve the required pressures required for haptic feedback. However, the aforementioned situation can be partly alleviated by the application of higher excitation Voltages, as the dielectric breakthrough Voltage of P(VDF-TrFE) is with 60 kV/cm [3] – 800 kV/cm [4] higher than that of PZT5H at 20 kV/cm [5].

This work investigates the feasibility of using PPTs for haptic feedback by investigating their performance using simulations and measurements of single PPTs and small arrays. The response of a chosen array design was subsequently predicted using the aforementioned results.

II. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Prototype devices

The PPTs were built using a polyimide substrate. The piezomaterial used was P(VDF-TrFE) and was deposited on top of the substrate using a printing process. The thickness of the P(VDF-TrFE) varied, but it was typically below 30 μm . The element connections were created using metallic electrodes and the element edges were formed using a thick organic material. The maximum thickness of the sheet was < 0.25 mm and was fully flexible.

A number of test devices were built, each containing a variety of PPTs. The diameter of the PPTs ranged from 1.5 – 12 mm. Moreover, the PPTs were grouped as single addressable elements, linear arrays (2, 5, 8 and 10 elements),

matrix arrays (3x3 or 5x5 elements) and annular arrays (10 rings, array diameter 35 mm). Two sheets filled with test devices are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. a) First sheet containing PPTs of various sizes. b) Second sheet containing PPTs in linear, matrix and annular array configurations.

B. Model description

The surface displacement, transfer functions, and acoustic far field response of PPTs with different geometries and materials were modeled in air. The model of the piezoelectric membrane was based on the description of Banks et al. [6]. Relevant for the PPTs were the piezo constants d_{31} and d_{32} and the effective surface moments associated with these piezo constants. The effective surface moments in the plane of the transducer were given by $E_{pe}/(1-\nu) \cdot e \cdot U \{d_{31}, d_{32}\}$ [6] in which E_{pe} was the modulus of the piezo material at constant strain, ν is Poisson's ratio, U the driving voltage, and e the distance between the midplane of the piezoelectric material and the neutral axis of the laminate [7]. Isotropic elastic properties were assumed for the piezoelectric material. The surface moments were transformed into a description based on line moments along the boundary of the electrode, such as in Ref. [8]. For a transducer with clamped boundaries these line moments vanished, if both the electrode and the piezoelectric layer covered the transducer completely [9]. Therefore, in case of clamped boundaries, either the electrode or the piezoelectric layer were to cover the transducer only partially. In the present case the piezoelectric layer was fully covering the transducer, whereas the electrode was covering the transducer only partially. Due to its small thickness, the mechanical properties of the electrode were neglected in the analysis. The model was implemented in the Comsol FEM package.

C. Vibrometer setup

Linear chirps (various center frequencies, -6 dB bandwidths 10 - 200 kHz, various amplitudes, 100 ms in length) were produced by a waveform generator (33250A, Agilent Technologies, Loveland Colorado, USA), amplified 100x (voltage gain) by a power amplifier (7500, Krohn-Hite Corporation, Brockton, MA, USA) and routed to a single or an array of custom built PPTs. The out-of-plane surface displacement of the object of interest was measured using a laser scanning vibrometer system. The object was mounted in an XYZ scanner system (A3200 Npaq, Aerotech Inc., Pittsburg PA, USA), such that the vibrometer could be used to scan the surface velocity of the object with a translation step size of 0.1 mm. The vibrometer system was based on a modular vibrometer (OFV-5000, Polytec GmbH, Waldbronn, Germany). The system used an OFV-552-1 differential fiber laser interferometer. The laser beam was focused at the object of interest using an OFV-MR lens. The laser spot size had a diameter of $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$. The vibrometer produced an analog output proportional to the measured velocity through either a VD-09 Digital Velocity Decoder or a DD-900 Digital Wide Range Decoder. The analog output was digitized using a digitizer (MI.3025, Spectrum Instrumentation, Grosshansdorf, Germany) with a sample frequency of 1 MHz. The digitizer also produced the trigger for the waveform generator.

D. Acoustic setup

Linear chirps (various center frequencies, -6 dB bandwidths 10 - 200 kHz, various amplitudes, 100 ms in length) were produced by a waveform generator (33250A, Agilent Technologies, Loveland Colorado, USA), amplified 40x (voltage gain) by a power amplifier (GPS 3400, Peavey Electronics Corporation, Meridian, MS, USA) and routed to a PPT. The emitted acoustic pressure was received by microphone (4138, Brüel & Kjaer, Naerum, Denmark) positioned on-axis at 30 cm distance from the source, amplified (SR560, Stanford Research Systems, Sunnyvale, CA, USA) and digitized (MI.4032, Spectrum Instrumentation, Grosshansdorf, Germany). The excitation Voltage over the electrodes was read-out using an electrical probe and digitized. The digitizer produced the trigger for the waveform generator.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Simulation and measurement results

The modeled and measured (with the vibrometer setup) fundamental mode resonance frequency versus the diameter of the PPT membrane is plotted in Fig. 2. The membrane vibrated in air. The modeled resonance frequencies are indicated by the dash-dotted blue lines with circles and the measured frequencies are indicated by the dashed red lines with crosses.

Fig. 2. The modeled (dash-dotted blue lines with circles) and measured (dashed red lines with crosses) fundamental resonance frequency versus membrane diameter. The medium was air.

Fig. 2 shows that the modeled and experimentally measured fundamental resonance frequencies were generally in good agreement. As expected, the resonance frequency scales as $1/\text{diameter}^2$. For larger elements the difference between the modeled and measured resonance frequency increased. This was likely caused by unexpected variations in the thickness and material properties of the P(VDF-TrFE) layer and the material used for the edges.

Fig. 3 displays the measured (solid blue line) and modeled (dashed purple line) sound pressure level (SPL) versus frequency for a 6 mm diameter PPT membrane at a 30 cm axial distance from the PPT. The excitation Voltage was 1 V.

Fig. 3. The modeled (dashed purple line) and measured (solid blue line) sound pressure level (SPL) versus frequency for a 6 mm diameter PPT at 30 cm axial distance from the source. The excitation Voltage was 1 V and the medium was air.

The results shown in Fig. 3 indicated that the simulations produced resonance frequencies of the first two symmetric modes at 3.2 kHz and 17 kHz, whereas the measured resonance frequencies of said modes were at 3.7 kHz and 16 kHz respectively. The SPL at 30 cm using a 1 V excitation amplitude at the fundamental resonance was modeled and measured to be ~17 dB re 20 μ Pa. In general there was good agreement between the model and measured results displayed in Fig. 3. The main difference was that the modeled peaks were considerably sharper compared to the measured peaks. A likely explanation was the uncertainty on the material properties, most notably the damping (i.e. viscoelastic behavior) in the material used to form the membrane edges.

Fig. 4 shows the measured peak out-of-plane surface displacement of a 2 mm diameter PPT excited at its fundamental resonance of 29.5 kHz using a 500 V chirp.

Fig. 4. Peak out-of-plane surface displacement of a 2 mm membrane excited at its fundamental resonance frequency using a 500 V chirp as measured using the laser vibrometer setup in air. The displacement was color coded (red = high displacement, green = 0 displacement) for better visualization. The red circle indicates the theoretical size of the membrane.

As can be observed in Fig. 4 the measured displacement of the 2 mm diameter PPT was circularly symmetric. The shape corresponded well to the first mode shape expected for a fully clamped circular plate [10]. The area indicating displacement was slightly larger than the 2 mm size of the membrane (red circle), which was caused by the fact 1) that the membrane edges were not exactly vertical and 2) that the material used to construct the edges was fairly soft. The peak out-of-plane surface displacement was 1.6 μ m at the PPT's resonance of 29.5 kHz using an excitation amplitude of 500 V (measured in air). The distortion of the measurement was low, as the measured 2nd harmonic was < -45 dB below the fundamental.

Fig. 5 displays the measured out-of-plane peak displacement versus the excitation Voltage for a 2 mm diameter PPT membrane. The PPT was excited at its resonance frequency of 29.5 kHz.

Fig. 5. Out-of-plane peak displacement versus excitation Voltage for a 2 mm membrane measured at the membranes resonance frequency (29.5 kHz).

As can be seen in Fig. 5 the out-of-plane peak displacement of the 2 mm diameter PPT at its resonance of 29.5 kHz had a linear relation with the excitation Voltage. The integrity of the PPT remained uncompromised even after several hours of continuous measurements. This was also the case for the other PPTs tested at high Voltages (up to 1500 V_{pp}).

Fig. 6 shows a snapshot of the measured out-of-plane displacement (arbitrary units), where a single ring of an annular array (ring 9 of the top left array in Fig. 1b, the ring numbering is in ascending order with the array radius) was excited. The snapshot was taken near the fundamental 65 kHz resonance of the membranes in the ring to show the various phenomena of interest. The excitation was a linear chirp with a 50 V amplitude.

Fig. 6. Out-of-plane displacement (in arbitrary units) recorded using the laser vibrometer setup where ring 9 of an annular array (top left array in Fig. 1b) was excited using a 50 V linear chirp. The rings are numbered in ascending order according to the array radius. The snapshot was taken near the fundamental 65 kHz resonance of the PPTs in the ring.

As can be seen from Fig. 6 roughly the top half of the PPTs in ring 9 worked in phase and had an approximately equal out-of-plane surface displacement amplitude. The PPTs in the bottom half of the ring vibrated with a different phase compared to that of the top half, as could be observed from the more greenish hue in the out-of-plane surface displacement of the PPTs in the bottom half of the ring. There was also more variation in the amplitudes and phases in the bottom half. At coordinates [5 mm, 15 mm] and [5 mm, 25 mm] there were groups of PPTs where some delamination had occurred explaining the unexpected displacement patterns (indicated by white circles). Other PPTs than those in ring 9 showed clear evidence of displacement. It was likely that most of that was due to acoustic crosstalk, which was caused by the large opening angle of the PPTs and by an A_0 Lamb wave propagating in the sheet itself. The A_0 wave is visible in Fig. 6 by the green rings outside of the array (see region A in Fig. 6).

B. Performance prediction chosen array design

Using the measurement results and modeling presented in the previous sections a PPT based array was designed. The array consisted of PPTs with a radius of 0.88 mm leading to a resonance frequency of 40 kHz. The array had an annular configuration on a square area of 30x30 cm² and was subdivided in 32 elements: 17 full rings and 15 ring-parts (to fill out the square). The fill grade was 50%. The focus was set to 0.3 m. The properties for air at 20°C and at 1 bar were used (density 1.2 kg/m³, acoustic wave speed 340 m/s, attenuation at 40 kHz 1.3 dB/m). The model results showed that the peak displacement of a single PPT at 40 kHz was 2.5 nm/V. Taking into account the membrane shape and the fill grade leads to a piston-like mean displacement of 0.42 nm/V. Using the gain factor for a focused circularly symmetric piston transducer (eq. 34 of [11]), a 500 V excitation amplitude and taking into account sound attenuation, one obtains a calculated peak pressure of 152 dB re. 20 μ Pa. Based on the equations reported by Nowicki et al. [12] an acoustic streaming peak velocity of 0.88 m/s was calculated. Using formula's used to calculate the force due to a liquid jet impinging on a stationary flat plate and assuming a tactile receptor radius of 1 cm this leads to a peak force due to acoustic streaming of 0.29 mN at focus. Using eq (1) of [1] an acoustic radiation force of 2.7 mN was calculated, which is approximately 1 order of magnitude higher than the tactile radiation force threshold of 0.3 – 0.4 mN reported in literature [13].

IV. CONCLUSION

Haptic feedback using PPTs appears feasible and realistic. Even more so, as the element design can be improved considerably in terms of efficiency. This paves the way for free space haptic feedback based on ultrasound, where the flexible and deformable sound sources are seamlessly integrated in other objects – e.g. car dashboards.

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